

Speculation on Quantum Tunneling

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We have argued in previous notes that it is special relativity which gives rise to the free particle probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. This probability is directly associated with physical behaviour because the somewhat random variables are x and t and while p and E are exact. One has probability in t and x for the interaction variables E, p . This suggests a kind of resonance feature, we argue. This idea of resonance seems to carry over into a single bound state and helps to explain why such a quantum system is associated with more than simply a statistical calculation.

Using $\exp(-ipx)$ as a probability for a time-independent problem (i.e. considering impulse hits in x only), one may mathematically express the average kinetic energy as: $\{\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)pp/2m \exp(ipx)\}/W(x)$, where $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$. One may then use: $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n$. As an average, one has different p values creating $KE_{ave}(x)$, with only the average KE plus $V(x)$ equalling E_n . The notion of conservation of energy, however, must hold and this begs the question: How is the energy for each p obtained such that energy is conserved. We suggest that the only source is $V(x)$ and so if one moves from a p_1 to a p_2 , at some x , then if $p_2 > p_1$, the extra kinetic energy must be borrowed from the potential energy. This is not simply an average calculation, energy conservation must be imposed. This suggests that a physical resonance is established, which allows for high p values using borrowed $V(x)$ energy. As a result, a quantum particle is not stopped at a classical turning point, but it receives its high p and passes this point using borrowed energy. The energy belongs to the potential $V(x)$ and the particle is not free to move off with the borrowed energy. We suggest that tunneling occurs with borrowed potential energy and that the simplest condition $W(x) \rightarrow \infty$ shows that a particle which escapes the classical turning point cannot go too far with its borrowed energy. The catch is that if another potential is placed near the classical turning point of the first, it can lend energy to the particle so that the borrowed energy from the first potential is returned and the particle is pulled into the second system, as seen in experiments. Thus, borrowed potential which is part of a resonance mechanism allows a quantum particle to bypass the classical turning point restriction and one can swap borrowed energy from one system to another to actually have a particle tunnel out of one bound system into another system.

Free Particle Wavefunction/Probability

We argue that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is a complex probability which demonstrates that E and p interactions appear with an associated probability at different t and x points. Time probability is linked with E and x separately with p impulse hits. There is an inherently probabilistic (due some physical mechanism) quantum particle with a $\Delta x = \hbar/p$. This has consequences on interactions as one can no longer argue that a particle p fits into $dx \rightarrow 0$ as in Newtonian mechanics and that a deterministic force $= -dV/dx$ acts within this dx . Nevertheless, the classical notion of work $pp/2m$ still holds as does energy conservation and momentum conservation. We argue that this view has implications on the notion of tunneling.

The Concept of An Average

An average is a statistical concept and does not imply the existence of a resonance. For example, one may have a set of completely independent results (scores of students' tests) and calculate an average. We suggest that one should not think of a quantum bound state problem in this manner. Mathematically, one may write:

$$\{\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) p^2 / 2m \exp(ipx)\} / W(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((1))$$

The first term on the LHS is $KE_{ave}(x)$ which implies that one may have on p or another. This begs the question: Where does the energy come from? We argue that it must come from the potential $V(x)$ if one is to have conservation of energy. In other words there are two statistical features to this problem, the inherent $\exp(ipx)$ of a particle and the $a(p)$ values. A particle can only have one p value at a time at a given point, but if one considers $V(x)$ as an average energy as well, then at a given x , one may have a p_1 with a certain amount of borrowed energy from $V(x)$, a p_2 with a different borrowed energy etc. This means that at a classical turning point:

$$KE_{ave}(x_1) = 0 \quad ((2))$$

One may p values greater than 0 because the particle has borrowed potential energy and it can exceed the classical turning point. The catch is that this particle cannot be considered to be a free particle (even for a square well potential) because it has "escaped" with borrowed potential energy which belongs to the bound system. It can only move a little outside the classical turning point according to the simplest constraint:

$$W(x) \rightarrow 0 \text{ for } x = \pm \infty \quad ((3))$$

Given that such an escaped particle contains borrowed potential energy, it could in principle swap this energy for borrowed potential energy from a second system very close to the classical turning point of the first. In such a case, the first potential does not lose its energy, but the so-called escape particle receives energy from the second system and can then move in that system with its provided energy. Thus, in experiments, there are two systems involved in a tunneling measurement.

If this view is to be taken seriously, then ((1)) may be rewritten as:

$$\{\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p) p^2 / 2m \exp(ipx)\} + V(x)W(x) = E_n W(x) \quad ((2))$$

This suggests that $V(x)$ be considered in terms of:

$$V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \text{ } V_k \exp(ikx) \quad ((3))$$

This is consistent with $\exp(ikx)$ conserving momentum in collisions with the potential. Enforcing such conservation of momentum directly in the interaction (assuming $V(x)$ is associated with an

infinite rest mass), means that conservation goes beyond the total $V(x)$ plus its rest mass associated system, but pertains to every collision with p . This may then explain how one obtains various p values for $\exp(ipx)$ and achieves the tunneling effect, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a quantum free particle probability $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ implies a physical resonance. In particular, impulse hits for p are probabilistically rendered in \hbar/p while the particle moves with $x=vt$. This result respects special relativity and conservation of momentum, e.g. $\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x)$ for a collision of two particles. We suggest that conservation of momentum and special relativity must be respected then for collisions with $V(x)$. It is possible to create a naive interpretation of $\{\text{Sum over } p \frac{a(p)p}{2m} \exp(ipx)\} / W(x) + V(x) = E_n$, if one only thinks in terms of averages. One may ask why one may have different p values at the same x when there is only one $V(x)$ value? This seems to violate conservation of energy. If one considers $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$, then one thinks in terms of $\{\text{Sum over } p \frac{a(p)p}{2m} \exp(ipx)\} + V(x)W(x) = E_nW(x)$. One may then have different p values at the same x due to borrowing energy from $V(x)$. This allows some p values to exceed the classical turning point, but they do not represent free particles because they contain borrowed $V(x)$ energy. Mathematically, the simplest constraint is $W(x) \rightarrow 0$ for $x = \pm\infty$. If a particle contains borrowed $V(x)$ energy and there is another system near the classical turning point of the first, it seems the particle could swap the energy from the first $V(x)$ and obtain new energy from $V_2(x)$ and become part of the second system. We suggest this as a possible explanation of tunneling.